

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CHILDREN FROM SOLO PARENT FAMILIES IN A SUBURBAN VILLAGE

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ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, the family is regarded as the cornerstone of social life. It is the basic unit of society and a very essential component of the country. Just like how atoms work to hold together the integrity of a matter, the family also functions as the most integral part of a country; for, without healthy Filipino families, expectations of a healthy Philippines can be hard to attain. The Child and Youth Welfare Code (P.D. 603) provides that every Filipino child has the right to a wholesome family life that will provide him with love, care and understanding, guidance and counseling, and moral and material security (Aliliran, 2022) However, this provision is being challenged incessantly as Filipino families today are beset with problems especially in keeping all provisions in the code together in a home to sustain their children's growth and development. These myriad challenges redound to fears for the future of the country's youth. The hope of the motherland is being challenged and bombarded with problems as they battle for existence and acceptance in today's world. Their homes, as well as their custodians, are beleaguered with problems of staying together to nurture their children and keep them safe so that they may become productive citizens in the community where they live in. This study explored the lived experiences of children in a solo-parent household and described how the children experienced the phenomenon. Moreover, it utilized the phenomenological research design – developed by Husserl, Heidegger, Sartre, Ponty; with origins dating back to Kant

and Hegel. It shed light and paved the way to an understanding of the plight of the children who experienced emotional wounds and disrupted goals and who ultimately become casualties when parents decide to end or digress from their marital vows. The family plays a crucial role in the holistic development of children. The home is where children are molded and honed in regards to psychological, social, and holistic development. Further, the role of parents who exemplifies love, respect, and sheer guidance to children cannot be relegated to the sides. Both parents play a crucial role in the growth and development of their children and cannot be over-emphasized. When done with utmost love, guidance, and concern, we can ascertain children who can be great leaders and ultimately, who can steer the wheel of success and who can be the hope of our nation in the near future.

Keywords: *Solo parent 1; Solo-parent families 2; phenomenological study 3*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, the family is regarded as the cornerstone of social life. It is the basic unit of society and a very essential component of the country. Just like how atoms work to hold together the integrity of a matter, the family also functions as the most integral part of a country; for without healthy Filipino families, expectations of a healthy Philippines can be hard to attain. To Filipinos, the word “family” can take on a variety of meanings, foremost is the presence of both parents taking care of their home, of each other, and battling the perils of everyday challenges that beset humankind. The family is also synonymous with “haven” to Filipinos, a place where members feel safe, comfortable and happy. Similarly, the family is where children learn from their parents that they have to act in a polite manner, to mingle with others and treat individuals with respect, courtesy and others (Kahur, 2018).

Essentially, the place where a family resides is referred to as a home. This is where its members, particularly the children can assimilate values as they work their way to become productive citizens of the country. The house, as opposed to the family, is where values are instilled that provide its members a perspective on life, a feeling of self, as well as a lens through which to see the world and their situations. Similarly, the home creates the basis of being: where parents play critical roles in molding the minds of young people who are capable of dealing with the problems of the times, and who are honed with good values, personality, and character that they can uphold throughout their lives.

The obstacles and hazards that families confront are an inevitable part of developing relationships within them. It is only natural that no one wants to lose the sense of security that comes with having a family. Difficulties and misunderstandings in any family is inherent no matter how perfect their connection is; it will be forever present as it is part of any relationship.

A child's life might be disrupted and confused by a broken home (<https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/2017/vol3issue2/PartG/3-2-106-798.pdf>). Their once-upon-a-time family that consists of both parents is now broken. The child is forced to grow up with a solo parent, battling unimaginable wars (poverty, crimes, etc.) the Philippine society today face --- alone, and perhaps hurting and bewildered.

According to Cabato (2018), the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) estimates that 3 million Filipino families have only one parent, with two million of those being led by single women, who face severe shame and pressure. Furthermore, according to the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), 14 million Single parents are one of the poorest and most vulnerable groups in Philippine society (De Vera, 2016).

The problem with solo parents has been a major challenge in the society that ought to be given enough attention as its effect to the children, the hope of the fatherland so to speak, is not short-lived. The wound inflicted by the separation and the circumstances that surround it can be so deep that it scars the child/children for the rest of their lives. Thus, this study explored on the lived experiences of children from solo parent families in a suburban village. It sought perspectives from participants as regards solo parenting and delved into their experiences in the hope that understanding these can provide a foundation for strengthening family relationships and perhaps provide a scheme to support children of solo parents thereby extenuating the challenges they face.

Theoretical Framework

This study is strongly hinged on Colaizzi's Phenomenological Framework for the specified research goals described by Morrow et al. (2015) which explored on the lived experiences of children of solo parent families as well as the Family Systems Theory developed by Murray Bowen (1960).

Colaizzi's phenomenological method for qualitative data analysis is a rigorous and sharp analysis process; it follows a distinct seven-step process that closely follows the gathered data. In this study, Colaizzi's method was employed, ruminating on the experiences of the children with solo parents.

The Family Systems Theory (Bowen, 1960) is another theory that this study is based on. In contrast to most child development and parenting theories, which focus on the individual or even the dyadic, systems theory regards the family as the primary emotional unit. This theory aims to explain social behavior and patterns of social interactions by gaining a better understanding of these interconnected systems. Patterns of intergenerational family interactions, given roles within the family, social triangulations, and the desire for all emotional systems to achieve and maintain balance influences behavior and emotional health.

In addition, the Family Systems Theory provides a number of concepts that are valuable in understanding triadic family relationships involving a mother, a father, and a child. The family is also seen as the primary emotional unit in the theory. Any change in one family member's emotional functioning is compensated for immediately and predictably by changes in other family members' emotional functioning. Understanding these interacting systems is the goal of family systems theory, which aims to explain social patterns and behavior. Patterns of intergenerational family interactions, given responsibilities within the family, social triangulations, and the desire to achieve and sustain equilibrium --- all emotional systems must work together and, are all said to have an impact on behavior and emotional health (McHale & Lindahl, 2011).

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the phenomenological research design – developed by Husserl, Heidegger, Sartre, Ponty; with origins dating back to Kant and Hegel.

In phenomenological research, which is a design of inquiry rooted from philosophy and psychology, the researcher describes the lived experiences of people regarding a phenomenon as told by participants. The core of various people's experiences who have all undergone the phenomenon lends substance to the study. This design has significant philosophical underpinnings (Giorgi, 2009 and Moustakas, 1994). As referred by Creswell (2014), this design often entails conducting interviews as well to delve into the participants' experiences so as concrete understanding of the phenomena is gained. This study conducted the interviews utilizing an interview guide and the data was analyzed using Colaizzi's qualitative data analysis method. The data were transcribed and the same were shown to the participants for verification if what were contained in the transcription were authentic and true.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants of the study were children from solo parent families in a suburban village. From the in-depth interview (IDI) conducted the discussion below encapsulates the themes that emerged.

According to the responses, of children raised by a single parent, the researchers discovered that being a single parent has detrimental consequences on youngsters. In general, children confront the same problems or challenges as adults do. The difficulties they experience, on the other hand, are proportional to their age. Social issues, psychological issues, educational issues, behavioral issues are all examples of these problems. Children raised by a single parent, on the other hand, have substantially greater problems than children reared by two parents (Smith, 2017). This matches the findings of Sigle-Rushton and McLanahan (2004), who conducted a similar study on the child's well-being when one parent is absent.

The outcomes of the study show that children raised by only one biological parent perform poorly than children raised by both biological parents on a range of social and economic parameters. Boys from single-parent households have more problems than girls, according to data. Furthermore, the intensity of problems faced by children in single-parent families is dictated by the age of the child at the time of their parents' divorce. The study's findings demonstrate that the trauma of single parenthood has a greater impact on younger children. Nancy's findings in 2001, as well as Price and McKenry's (1998) investigation, back up the previous findings. According to their study, the consequences of divorce or being a single parent are more severe for boys than for girls.

In addition to economic problems, single parenthood has a negative impact on children's psychological wellbeing which somehow created in them emotional wounds in the statements from the interviews:

Nasulub-on gihapon maam kay bagan nakikita mo man nga hi mama bagan nagkukuri na [I feel sad when I see my mother's hardship) (R5, Line 459-460)

Nakukuan gad ako. . . **na sa sad ako kay diri na kami kompleto kay hi mama na manla iton amon kaupod.** [I feel sad that we are not complete, we only have our mother with us] (R6, Line 735-736)

Masakit ko ha dughan nga nasusugad hi mama...kami nasugad hini ba..nakakatuok ako kay nabalik adto ngan masakit para ha akon in inga kabutang [It pains me that mama experienced this...we got into this... I feel like crying because I am reminded of the pain for what we got into] (R4, L 308-311)

Also, the social wellbeing of the children is affected as well inasmuch as children inherently would aspire for the warmth and companionship of their family on special occasions and have a sense of belongingness and be “like the rest of the gang.” These were manifested in the participants’ narrative as exemplified below:

“Iton nag expect kasi ton .. Iton pag graduation ko .. Or iton pag birthday ko.. Ngan akon debut wray hira kumada.. Amo adto **mamingaw tak birthday** amo kumada nala tak mga classmates..amo adto .”[I was expecting that during my graduation or birthday they will be around, sadly they weren’t there, so I just went to my classmates] (R7, Line 878-880)

A study on the family’s role on the development of positive behavior on children show that positive behavior of parents in their daily routines and social support are important in their child’s social development. Since children mostly learn by example, the mere experience of how their parents show affection in their day-to-day dealings at home and the parents’ support on the child’s social activities also manifests in how their children interact with others outside of their families (Roy and Giraldo-Garcia, School Community Journal, 2018, Vol. 28, No. 2). On the other hand, some children from solo-parent families, through own need to find answers to life’s perplexing questions, can find solace in religion; and from their develop positive values through their own volition as shown in the responses narrated by one of the participants: “Kuan po .. Nakadto po ako ha simabahan, nag aampo [I just go to church and pray] (R7, Line 957). This was when she feels alone and lonely and in need of comfort.

The study of Roy and Giraldo-Garcia (2018) on the role of parental involvement and social/ emotional skills in academic achievement found that both parents and the school community need to make a conscious and intentional effort to facilitate the development of academic and social/emotional skills in children Educational well-being. On the contrary, children with solo parent manifested otherwise as manifested in the lines below. This was expressed by one of the participants who narrated this heart-wrenching explanation when asked about how having a solo parent affected his studies:

“Han during han ano namon, elementary days hi mama perme ito hiya waray ngada ha balay , **gin-babaya**an kami axa waray ako pagtuhay.” [During my elementary days, my mother is always not around which is the reason that I didn’t do well in school] (R5, Line 494-495)

Conclusions

The family plays a crucial role in the holistic development of children. The home is where children are molded and honed as regards psychological, social and holistic development. Further, the role of parents who exemplifies love, respect and sheer guidance to children cannot be relegated to the sides. Both parents play crucial role in the growth and development of their children and cannot be over-emphasized. When done with utmost love, guidance and concern, we can ascertain children who can be great leaders and ultimately, who can steer the wheel of success and who can be the hope of our nation in the near future.

Compliance with ethical standards

The respondents voluntarily participated to the research study conducted by the researchers from Eastern Visayas State University. The respondents understand that the research is designed to gather the data for the study. They were allowed to ask questions about the project and their participation. Moreover, the use of the data in research, publication, sharing and archiving has been explained thoroughly. They further agreed that taking part in the project would include being interviewed and recorded (Audio or Video) provided that their identity are kept confidential and they have the freedom to withdraw anytime. After the data were transcribed and confirmed by the respondents, the recordings were destroyed.

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